

A New Policy for Mountain Small Farms: A Discrete Choice Experiment for a Labor-Based CAP Scheme

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Answering the question “what is a small farm?” is tricky. There is no broad consensus on how to define them (European Parliament, 2014). For our purposes we adopted an operational definition to classify farms as small when their standard output is below EUR 25,0

00. According to the Agricultural Census 2010, 81% of Italian farms fall below this threshold (60% in Lombardy). The relative importance of small farms increases in the mountain territories. In Lombardy mountains they represents 82%, of farms, and 61% of working units.

Many studies have demonstrated that mountain agriculture provides a range of ecosystem services such as water regulation, soil conservation, biodiversity conservation, and carbon sequestration. Furthermore, it plays a crucial role in preserving local cultures and food, and traditional knowledge. Small farming in the mountains also fosters rural development, generating employment opportunities.

However, despite its importance, mountain agriculture, it is now facing various challenges that threaten its sustainability. The number of mountains farms is continuously decreasing (Schuh et al., 2022), with very low generational renewal rates (Cavicchioli et al., 2015). One of the most immediate consequences is land abandonment, which in turn brings undesirable effects such as changes in biodiversity and ecosystem services, and rural viability. According to Dax et al. (2021) EU land abandonment risk is three times higher in mountain areas than elsewhere.

The EU, through the CAP, claims to assist small farms. However, CAP tools have not always been able to support small farms. In the Lombardy mountains only 32.5% farms receive CAP directs payments, share reduced to 22.7% among small farms. Obviously, area payments do not fit with small mountain farm’s characteristics, largely excluding them from CAP beneficiaries.

Given the role played by mountain small farms in managing territory, and in contrasting mountains abandonment, a paradigm shift in CAP support for this type of farms would be desirable. As a consequence we propose a new CAP policy scheme, tailored to mountain small farms, with a yearly payment per working unit, and conditioned to the respect of environmental and labour commitments. Although CAP payments are given per unit area, a payment per labour unit, the mountain small farmer’s scheme (henceforth MSFS) proposes a payment per working unit. This would provide an incentive for people to stay in the mountains as a key factor for territory management and viability.

This paper aims to assess, by a DCE (Discrete choice experiment), the willingness of small mountain farmers to join MSFS, in order to: i) measure in monetary terms small farmers’ favour or aversion to some potential entry conditions to the scheme, and ii) simulate the potential participation among the entire population of farmers and iii) estimating the costs of such policy implementation.

To better design the MSFS, focus groups with mountain small farmers were organized to gather insights on the attributes of the hypothetical scheme. It is characterised by three attributes. The first two are conditions to participate in the small farms scheme: an environmental condition and a commitment condition.

The last attribute is an annual payment per each agricultural working unit (AWU) employed in the farm. Employment on the farm was certified by the worker's registration with the agricultural insurance scheme. The

farmer and each possible family helper were accounted as 1 AWU, such as each full time hired worker, while each part-time hired worker was accounted as 0.5 AWU.

Attributes and levels used in the DCE are listed in the table below (table 1).

Table 1 – Description of attributes and levels

Attributes	Levels	
Environmental condition (<i>environ</i>)	 Environmental certification required	Level 1: To receive the new small farmers scheme, the farm is required to have an environmental certification (e.g. organic farming or low-input farming)
	 Environmental certification not required	Level 0: no environmental condition
Commitment condition (<i>3years</i>)	 3-year contract	Level 1: triennial commitment (the farm must maintain its AWUs for 3 years and receives full payment at the end of this period; if does not maintain the commitment it only receives 50% of the expected annual payments)
	 1-year contract	Level 0: annual commitment (each year, the farm receives payment based on the number of AWU present in the farm in that year and each year can decide whether to opt out of the new payment system)
Monetary condition	Annual payment for each AWU in the farm	1,000 €/year; 2,500 €/year; 4,000 €/year

The environmental condition has two levels: in level 1 the farm undertakes to acquire an environmental certification (organic farming and/or low-input farming).

The commitment attribute particularly ties in with the objectives of the small farms scheme. This attribute aims to ensure that agricultural work units remain on the mountains as long as possible. The commitment attribute presents two levels: level 0 (1-year contract) and level 1 (3-years contract). Level 0 is the less demanding, requiring an annual commitment for which farmers are paid annually depending on the AWUs present each year. In level 1 the farm undertakes to join the scheme for a period of three years during which it will be obliged not to reduce its initial work units.

The monetary level takes the form of an annual payment given for each worker employed in the farm. This payment is intended to replace all CAP First Pillar payments to which the farm would be entitled. We set three levels for this attribute (1,000/2,500/4,000 €/AWU)

Each choice card includes three possible policy options, among which farmers were requested to make a choice. The first two options indicates two alternative small farms schemes differing for one or more attributes. The last option is the ‘*status quo*’ option, stated by the sentence ‘I prefer my current situation’.

To the purpose of our research, a group of Lombardy mountain farmers received an online questionnaire. Potential respondents were chosen among farms with a SO lower than EUR 25,000. A set of six choice cards was presented to respondents. After a pilot study, we proposed the questionnaire to about 250 farms, obtaining 172 valid answers (69% response rate).

Applying the same sample selection criteria, we quantified the size of the target universe, determinable in about 6,000 farms. Therefore, our DCE covered about the 3% of all represented farms. Statistics about the DCE sample and the related universe are presented in table 1.

Table 1 - Descriptive statistics

Lombardy mountain farms with SO<25,000€	DCE sample: 172 farms	2020 administrative data: 5,956 farms
Average utilized agricultural area (UAA)/farm (ha)	4.94	5.75
Average standard output (SO)/farm (€)	12044	4818
Specialized fruit and vineyards	19.8%	34.2%
Specialized livestock production	41.3%	46.9%
Specialized arable crops	22.1%	7.2%
Average age of the farm (years)	14.15	18.65
Average elevation of municipality (meters)	977	1,082
Average CAP 1 st pillar payments/farm	1,061	958
% of farms with environmental certification	8.1%	3.1%
% of young farmers	24.4%	16.2%
Average number of working units (AWU) with social security contribution	1.05	Not available

To estimate DCE parameters, we used a random parameter mixed logit (RPL) model, allowing us to estimate individual parameters for the environmental and commitment conditions, and the Alternative Specific Constant (ASC_AB). Table 2 shows the results of the RPL estimation. As each of the 172 respondents made a choice for six choice cards with three alternatives, the total number of observations is $n=3,096$ ($172*6*3$).

All estimated coefficients are statistically significant at the 1% level. The negative coefficient of ASC_AB suggests a slight preference for retaining the current First Pillar payments, irrespective of the amount of the proposed SMFS payment. Notably, the ASC_AB coefficient is not statistically significant among farmers who do not currently receive any CAP subsidies.

Coefficients related to attributes show economic coherence. *Payment* coefficient is positive, while both those of *Environmental_condition* and *Duration_Condition* are negative. This means that farmers consider the conditions for participation in the scheme demanding, on average, and need further compensation to be fulfilled.

Table 2 – DCE parameters estimation

Parameters	Model: ALL		Model: YES_CAP		Model: NO_CAP	
	coeff.	sign.	coeff.	sign.	coeff.	sign.
Estimated coefficients						
<i>Payment</i>	0.00116 *** (0,000088)		0.00143 *** (0,000130)		0.00084 *** (0,000110)	
<i>Environm_cond</i>	-1.90747 *** (0,302)		-2.7529 *** (0,440)		-0.87441 ** (0,392)	
<i>Duration_cond</i>	-1.84328 *** (0,235)		-1.84671 *** (0,334)		-1.93132 *** (0,320)	
<i>ASC_AB</i>	-0.70579 *** (0,269)		-1.10519 ** (0,432)		-0.22839 (0,315)	
S.D. of random coefficients						
<i>Environm_cond</i>	2.96709 *** (0,350)		3.08113 *** (0,470)		2.51287 *** (0,447)	
<i>Duration_cond</i>	1.93273 *** (0,267)		2.29241 *** (0,366)		1.37617 *** (0,346)	
<i>ASC_AB</i>	1.97760 *** (0,272)		2.90216 *** (0,493)		0.95316 *** (0,358)	
Willingness to accept						
<i>Environm_cond</i>	1,649.30 ***		1,927.10 ***		1,045.90 **	
<i>Duration_cond</i>	1,593.80 ***		1,292.70 ***		2,310.30 ***	
<i>ASC_AB</i>	610.29 ***		773.67 ***		273.20	
Log-likelihood	-1,133.77		-725.08		-408.68	
Observations	3,096		1,980		1,116	
N. of farmers	172		110		62	

standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01; ** p<0.05; * p<0.10

It is worth of nothing that the MSFS acceptability varies across respondents based on the current level of CAP payments. Remembering that MSFS is proposed as an alternative to existing CAP payments, it is reasonable that farms with higher CAP subsidies would be less attracted by the new scheme, and vice versa (Fig.1).

Fig.1 - Small farmers' choices according to CAP first pillar payments classes

Later, we tried to simulate the rate of enrolment in SMFS in the universe of Lombardy mountain small farmers ($N=5.956$). Each respondent in the sample (and his/her individual estimated parameters) has been matched to similar individuals in the universe. In so doing we were able to compare for each small farmer in the universe the utility related to the *status quo* option and that deriving from participation in a SMFS.

To perform this comparison we have hypothesized three possible SMFS, defined by different combinations of levels of each attribute:

- SMFS 1: with the environmental condition, and duration condition set to one year;
- SMFS 2: without the environmental condition, and duration condition set to three years;
- SMFS 3: with the environmental condition, and duration condition set to three years.

For each SMFS and each level of the payment attribute, we estimated the individual utilities deriving from staying at the status quo and that from participating in each SMFS. When the latter is higher, that indicates the farmer would participate to the scheme in exchange for the payment for AWU offered. In Fig.2 we plotted the simulated rates of enrolment to the three SMFSs for different level of payments.

Fig.2 - Simulated participation rates for each SMSF program ($n=172$)

As expected SMFS 3 presents the lowest enrolment rate, spanning from 20.8% to 42.1%, when offered EUR 1,000 and EUR 4,000 per AWU per year, respectively. Differently, SMFS 1 and SMFS 2 would be more successful, gaining greater acceptance up to the level of 75 per cent for SMFS1 at the payment level of EUR 4,000 per AWU per year.

As previously observed the level of first pillar payments to be renounced when participating in a SMFS plays a key role in determining farmers' choices to enrol or not in the scheme. Consequently we also calculated probability of participation for each level of SMSF payment by discriminating by ranges of annual CAP First Pillar Payments (Fig.3).

Fig.3 - Simulated participation rates for each SMSF program and range of CAP First Pillar payments (n=172)

Generally, we found confirmation that the greater is the current CAP support the lower is the probability of participation in an SMSF, and vice versa.